

Short communication

First records of the southeastern mountain stink bug *Risibia christophi* (Jakovlev, 1886) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) for the Golan Heights and Mount Lebanon

ROLAND LUPOLI¹

¹ 79, rue Jules Ferry, F-94120 Fontenay-sous-Bois, France; e-mail: lupoli@free.fr;

² Immenweide 83, D-22523 Hamburg, Germany; e-mail: tmvdh@web.de

Abstract. The first records of *Risibia christophi* (Jakovlev, 1886) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) from the Golan Heights and Mount Lebanon are reported. The species is photographed alive in its natural environment for the first time. The distribution map of the species is included.

Key words: true bugs, Pentatomoidea, distribution, new record, Middle East, Golan Heights, Anti-Lebanon, Mount Hermon, Mount Lebanon, Cyprus.

Introduction

Species of the genus *Risibia* Horváth, 1888 are found in high mountains, generally at altitudes above 1,600 m, in Siberia, Middle Asia, Transcaucasia and Asia Minor (Ribes & Pagola-Carte 2013). The genus *Risibia* comprises four species: *R. christophi* (Jakovlev, 1886), *R. obscura* (Jakovlev, 1880), *R. verbasci* Lodos & Önder, 1980, and *R. xanthochila* Horváth, 1888 (Horváth 1888; Rider 2006).

These four species all share the same characteristic habitus, making them easy to distinguish from other Pentatomidae species: an oval body of uniform brownish colouration (including legs and antennae) with prominent dark punctation, of medium size (9–12 mm) with a narrow ivory-yellow border on the anterior lateral edges of the pronotum (which are straight), as well as on the edges of the corium and connexivum, and a U-shaped spot bordering the apex of the scutellum (Fig. 1).

Risibia xanthochila is found eastwards from the mountains of Iran to Siberia. A photograph of this species is available on the following website (accessed 01.06.2025): https://www.ndsu.edu/faculty/rider/Pentatomoidea/Genus_Carpocorini/Risibia.htm.

Risibia obscura is known only from Iran, while *R. verbasci* is known from only one locality in Türkiye (Konya: Doganhisar-Destigin) (Lodos & Önder 1980).

Risibia christophi (Fig. 1) is known from Türkiye: Kulp, Akbez; from Armenia: Hrazdan, Yerevan; from Azerbaijan (Nakhichevan): Ordubad, Unus; and from Iran: Karaj (Tehran), Gharahghach (Semiroom), Tabriz (Hoberlandt 1997, Rider 2006, Ribes & Pagola-Carte

2013). It has also been observed in Cyprus: Troodos (Artemis trail), at latitude 34.9285, longitude 32.8716, 1,823 m, on 24.06.2006, a female on *Cupressus* sp., Armand Matocq leg., det. Armand Matocq. The photo of this specimen is included in Plate VIh of the book by Ribes & Pagola-Carte (2013), but the authors failed to mention the presence of this species in Cyprus in their monograph (pp. 285-286). It was reported from Syria, but it is Akbez, formerly known as Akbes, which was located in Syria and is now found in Türkiye (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. *Risibia christophi* (Jakovlev, 1886) specimen observed on the ground alive on 20.05.2025 on the massif of Mount Hermon (Golan Heights) (photo: Omer Netanel).

Risibia christophi is stockier and larger than *R. verbasci*, has deeper punctation, and the yellow border on the anterolateral borders of the pronotum is very thin and not outlined by a narrow black line (Ribes & Pagola-Carte 2013).

Material examined

Golan Heights: Mount Hermon massif, latitude: 33.3023, longitude: 35.7898, 2,060 m, 20.05.2025, 1 specimen found crawling on the ground (Fig. 1), photo Omer Netanel, det. Roland Lupoli. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/284825344> (accessed 01.06.2025). This is the first photograph of this species alive and in its native environment.

Mount Lebanon: Mount Sannine, Matn, latitude: 33.9620, longitude: 35.8350, 2,090 m, 01.07.2025, 1 specimen found on the ground in a small hole (Fig. 2), photo Ramy Maalouf, det. Ori Fragman-Sapir. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/294530387> (accessed 02.07.2025).

Fig. 2. *Risibia christophi* (Jakovlev, 1886) specimen observed on the ground alive on 01.07.2025 on the massif of Mount Lebanon (Lebanon) (photo: Ramy Maalouf).

Fig. 3. Map of the Middle East. The red dots represent the locations where *Risibia christophi* (Jakovlev, 1886) has been observed, and the black dots represent the capitals of the respective countries. ©2019 <http://www.comersis.com/> (map cropped and modified).

Discussion

Risibia christophi is a mountain species found between 1,600 and 2,400 m above sea level. Its distribution is restricted to specific mountain ranges in the Near East, between 30° and 40° north latitude and 32° and 52° east longitude.

This rare species was previously known from the eastern edge of the Taurus Mountains in Türkiye, in the Armenian Highlands, and extended into Iran via the Zagros Mountains and the Elborz Mountains. Here, we report for the first time its presence in the Levant in the Golan Heights in the Anti-Lebanon Mountains and on Mount

Lebanon. We also confirm its presence in Cyprus in the Troodos Mountains (Fig. 3).

This fragmented distribution in the mountains can be explained by phases of late Pleistocene glaciation and warming, which would have allowed a series of continuities and separations between these populations now isolated from each other by desert zones or the sea (Sarıkaya & Çiner 2017).

References

- Hoberlandt L. 1997. Results of the Czechoslovak-Iranian entomological expeditions to Iran 1970, 1973 and 1977. Heteroptera: Acanthosomatidae, Cydnidae, Scutelleridae, Pentatomidae. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* **44** (1995): 181–294.
- Horváth G. 1888. Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Hémiptères de la faune paléarctique. *Revue d'Entomologie, publiée par la Société Française d'Entomologie* **7** (5): 168–189.
- Lodos N., Önder F. 1980. Two new species of Pentatomidae from Turkey (Heteroptera). *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi* **4**: 7–13.
- Ribes J., Pagola-Cardé S. 2013. Hémiptères Pentatomidae euro-méditerranéens. Volume 2. Systématique : deuxième partie sous-famille Pentatominae (suite et fin). *Faune de France* **96**. Fédération Française des Sociétés de Sciences Naturelles, Paris. 424 pp.

Acknowledgements

We wish to thank Omer Netanel and Ramy Maalouf for their permission to publish their observations and photos of *R. christophi*, as well as Armand Matocq for providing the coordinates of the *R. christophi* he observed in Cyprus.

Rider D.A. 2006. Family Pentatomidae Leach, 1815, pp. 233–402. [in:] Aukema B. & Rieger C. (eds.), *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region. Volume 5. Pentatomomorpha II*. The Netherlands Entomological Society, Amsterdam. 550 pp.

Sarıkaya M.A., Çiner A. 2017. Late Quaternary glaciations in the eastern Mediterranean, pp. 289–305. [in:] Hughes P.D. & Woodward J.C. (eds.), *Quaternary Glaciation in the Mediterranean Mountains. Special Publications* **433**. The Geological Society, London. 315 pp.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License
<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Received: 5 June 2025

Final version received: 11 July 2025

Final version accepted: 21 July 2025